
Ethnic Consciousness: The Bane to Economic and Socio-Political Development of Nigeria.

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Abstract

Nigeria is a Nation of varied Ethnic Nationalities. Research, shows that the Ethnic groups of the country is above 370. As a result, the cultural expressions of these groups varied socially, and politically. In effect, this should have been a source of strength to the nation, but instances have proved otherwise. Prior to the amalgamation of the Southern and Northern Protectorate into a Nation Nigeria, these groups have remarkably evolved peaceful means of promoting inter-ethnic relationship. The relationship had remained cordial for years, and extended through the political, economic and social spectrums of the people. At that time, the inter-ethnic conflicts were irregular, unsophisticated and occurred sparingly. The British intervention though might have instigated a kind of positive results, but its consequences on group's relationship more so on politics sphere are devastating. In effect, the amalgamation of the Southern and Northern protectorate adversely punctuated socio-economic and the political order of the Niger-area groups. The impact of this unholy accord is obvious, even as recent studies have shown the rising ethnic induced tensions in the polity as a fall out. Already one of such has resulted into full blown civil war. The mistrust which characterizes our present predicament has a direct link to the forceful integration of the groups by the British Colonists. Under the strange political institution deliberately imposed by the British, the confusion generated thereof have continued to hunt the unity of nation. In this state of quagmire, lies the fear of domination and lack of patriotism needed to build a new nation. In this presentation we have devoted our time to reminiscence on the ethnic characters of the country, the impact of the British amalgamation on the ethnic political, social and economic

development. We have also looked at the problems of the ethnic loyalty, and its effect on Nation building and concluded by subscribing to re-kindling the pre colonial bond of unity sustained through peaceful inter-group trade, which was established among the people as perceived solutions. In that case, the groups are expected to extend the spirit of peaceful trade to the spirit of peaceful political co-habitation. This, it is believed will contribute to establish generally acceptable political solution, that will be accommodating which we believe would help in our collective aspiration toward building an egalitarian society we can be proud of.

KEYWORDS: Nation Building, Ethnic Politics, Colonialism, Amalgamation and Party Politics.

INTRODUCTION.

Nigeria occupies the land space of about 924,000 square kilometer, and is the largest Country in land mass in West Africa. With the population of over 200 million people, it is not only the largest Country in Africa but the entire black world. ‘The country is dissected by its two main rivers, the Niger and Benue, and their many tributaries, which , joining together in the area around Lokoja in present day Kogi State, flow into Atlantic Ocean through the Niger Delta’. The Country is washed by Gulf of Guinea; on the west and north, it is bordered by the Republic of Dahomey and Niger; on the east it adjoins the Cameroon Republic. Its greatest length from South to North IS 650 miles and its maximum breadth from East to West is rather more than 750 miles.

Nigeria is situated wholly in the tropics and experience raining and dry season. Rainfall is heavier in the south and is known to start from April till October and dry season from November to March. The vegetation differs with the mangrove of noticeable in the Niger Delta area. Rainfall belt covers the most southern part of the Country with receding wooded grassland within the middle belt of the Country. Further North is the South of Sahel desert where annual rainfall is much lower.

Nigeria’s immense geographical space, with both physical and human, has had great impact on the development of the Country’. For instance, in the forest belt such agricultural produce or resources are found in abundance, such include timber, palm produce, cocoa, rubber, yam, rice, fruits and vegetable. Those in the mangrove belt have fishes, shrimps etc as key products. Apart from the agricultural products, Nigeria is endowed with mineral resources such resources include crude oil, gold, limestone, coal, bauxite etc. From the forgone, every part of Nigeria is naturally endowed. The groups have been living in healthy relationship before the arrival of the British colonial administrators. This is to say, that people of Niger-area had no ethnic contention as it were now. Challenges then was not political but Economic although policy of expansionism was practiced by superior Authorities, but close ties through marriage among groups tended to have calmed the nerves. Ethnicity was low then, and was almost absent because there was mutual understanding guiding every act as it relate with groups relationship.

But when this sense of freedom was denied the groups through colonial conquest, the state of despair gave room to mistrust when a group gained more recognition to the Colonial government than the other. The drive to restore personal freedom placed the groups at logger head, colonialism therefore arouse ethnic consciousness among once very peaceful groups who lived devoid contentions. It is therefore of the researcher’s opinion that ethnic consciousness in Nigeria was created by the colonial administrators.

ETHNIC COMPOSITION AND THE ORIGIN OF ETHNIC CONSCIOUSNESS IN NIGERIA.

According to research people have been living Nigeria since 2,500BC. In affirmation, Okon Uya has stated, thus, 'the area of present day Nigeria has been a stage upon which the drama of human development and cultural differentiation has been played over a long span of time dating back several centuries'. With the above assertion, it is obvious that people have been living in Nigeria for years. In fact, the discovery of the NOK Culture aptly proved the existence of the stone culture people in Nigeria. This argument is further made strong due to the fact, that, 'the presence of iron technology in the form of the manufacture of hand axe, bow, furnace, spear heads, hoes and axes, allow us to confirm that the Nigerian region had been extensively inhabited by sedentary populations with reasonably large scale political structure'.

In effect, that is not to say movement in and out did not take in the pre historic years in Nigeria. In fact, in southern Nigeria the Ibibio, Efik and Ejegham people are known to have migrated from Cameroon to settle in Nigeria. The Yoruba people of western Nigeria are known to have claimed the Middle East as their place of migration. The Fulani people are known to have arrived Nigeria as herdsmen from Fuota Djallon and Fouta Toro, presently in Senegal. The dominant tribe in the North, the Hausa has also made claims of the Middle East as their putative place of origin.

Nevertheless, the account of some ethnic groups in Nigeria, have shown certain moment of movement to their present location, in their tradition of origin. By indication, no group has claimed rooted in their present locality without a kind of movement and inter-cultural exchange. As it is today, Nigeria is made up of three major ethnic groups, the Igbo, Hausa and Yoruba. There are others with appreciable population like the Ijaw, Ibibio, Igala, Idoma, Tiv, Uroboho, Jukun, Itshekiri, Birom, Igbira, Fulani, Angas, Lantang, Yakur etc.

The three ethnic groups are dominant in the following regions of Nigeria, thus, Igbo, Ibibio, EfikEkoi in the south east. Yoruba, Ijaw, Uroboho, Itshekiri, Bini, in the south west. While in the North, the Hausa, Fulani, Tiv, Kanuri, Birom, Lantang, Angas, Jukun, Igala, Idoma, Nupe are predominant in the North. Ethnic groups are distinguished by language and custom. At times, types of clothes worn and food eaten could differentiate ethnic groups.

Nigeria as a Nation State came into existence in 1914 following the amalgamation of the Southern and Northern Protectorates. By that virtue it is the creation of the British Colonial Administration. The Country is made up of over 300 ethnic Nationalities, with each of them holding very strong to its sectional identities. It has been postulated that, the ethnic Nationalities were forcefully joined in what is now known as the unholy marriage in 1914, with the attendant consequence, being weak drive to facilitate the act of the Nation building by the moieties.

As a result of the strong cleavage to ethnic Nationalism, it has become very difficult to build strong link for the sake of promoting National consciousness. In effect, Party Politics that ought to have been the driving force toward building strong Nation State, have been hijacked by ethnic jingoist. The danger portend by this attitude is that Nigeria is seen as a National Cake that must be shared hot. In the course of enjoying larger cut, the wheel of Nation building has been truncated by the activities of the ethnic groups.

For years Ethnicism has spread to every stratum of Nigerian society. It has drowned whatever effort aimed at arousing National Consciousness. It has also breed corrupt tendencies and

thus has continued to propel the Nation on downward slide. Ethnicism has mortgaged merit for mediocrity; and this has created state of disharmony among groups. The fear of domination, and the desire to hoist mediocrity, has remained the key factor responsible for the underdevelopment in Nigeria.

THE POLARIZATION ETHNICISM IN POLITICS, SOCIAL LIFE AND THE ECONOMIC SECTORS IN NIGERIA.

Ethnicity has been defined as a group of people that have common identity, common goal because they have common origin and kinship ties. In addition, ethnicity or ethnic group could possess a common language and a common culture. Tribalism which is viewed derogatory in character has been used by some western scholars in reference to ethnicity. In Europe and North America, ethnicity has assumed the posture of nationalism. In that regard, it has denied a heterogeneous society the basis of nation building, since group now pay more attention to sectional interest rather than national or collective goals. Nwabughuogu aptly supported the above assertion when he stated thus, 'Ethnicity is generally believed to be a major hindrance to the process of nation building in Africa'. This is true because ethnicity project sectional interest, which encourages contention among groups. In Nigeria it has spread beyond covetous of political leadership to the entire aspect of group relationship.

The genesis of ethnicity in Nigeria has been traced to politics where it was believed among the groups, that whoever controls political leadership over other groups controls the machinery of authority in other aspect of groups endeavour. So the fear of domination was responsible for the ethnic politics in Nigeria. This assertion has received strong backing from Okechukwu Ikejiani, who stated in his book, thus, 'the NPC and AG introduced ethnic nationalism into Nigeria politics' ⁷Before Ikejiani's submission, two factors have laid credence to the above submission, for instance, Chief Obafemi Awolowo, one of the leading Nigerian politicians in the first and second republic is accredited to have said in his book titled 'Path to Nigerian Freedom', that, 'Nigeria was not a Nation, but a collection of many ethnic Nationalities'. This tendency has shaped Chief Awolowo's political expression. In fact, this could have informed Awolowo's decision when 'Egbe Omo Oduduwa' was formed. This cultural organization, which was initially formed for all the Oduduwa descendants (The founder of Yoruba), subsequently transformed to a political party in 1951, to actualize sectional interest. This is to the detriment of nation building.

Another incidence that happened to show case ethnic politics in Nigeria, happened during the western Nigeria regional election of 1952. Barely one year after the 'Egbe Omo Oduduwa' a cultural organization was formed, it has transformed to a political party. In that election the major party the NCNC has fielded candidates together with the newly formed party of Chief Awolowo the AG. After the election, out of the 84 seats contested for, the NCNC has won 43 seats. Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe, the leader of the NCNC, had contested for one of the seats for Lagos and won. From the above account, it was obvious that Dr. Azikiwe was going to be the first Premier of the western region, but this was never to be as Chief Awolowo, a Yoruba man whose region was to be ruled by Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe, an Igbo man from the Eastern region. In this case merit not only mortgaged but sectional interest hoisted above the national interest. In fact, when Awolowo instigated the notorious 'carpet crossing that resulted in an increase in the number of seats won by the AG to 42 and reduced the NCNC seats from 43 to 23'. Dr. Michael Okpara a prominent NCNC leader had referred the above incidence, 'as one of the greatest manifestations of tribalism in this country because it was done for no other reason than that Zik was an Igbo'.

In effect, it was not only Chief Awolowo's AG that exhibited the trait of ethnic politics, in fact, the NPC which was formed in 1949 'was the first political party to engender ethnic consciousness, thereby introducing ethnic nationalism in Nigerian politics'. Through its motto which was 'one North, One people and one destiny' the party became opposed to political ideologies other than that of the NPC.

Socio-politically, after the Second World War, the world attention was focused decolonization of Africa. Some of the disengaged African soldiers have returned home without job. Those who could not go back to the village stayed back in the cities in search of work. It was the town union members who have secured job that offered accommodation and food for the unemployed pending when they are able to secure job. It was therefore the activities of the town union and the cultural organization that contributed to strengthen the bond of ethnic nationalism.

It should however be noted, that nationalism was a strange ideology which in actual sense was externally or indirectly, or internally or directly induced. It was indirectly induced because the directors during the colonial era were none Nigeria. Michael Crowder corroborated by saying, thus, 'At first Nigeria Nationalism was largely promoted by non-Nigeria'. The non-Nigerians were the ex-slaves who returned to Africa with their colleagues who were in the western countries fighting racial discrimination. Others were African elites who had the opportunity to enjoy western education, and had experienced racial discrimination, when they returned home, they join the Pan Africanist to fight against colonialism. In effect, instead of the elites to sustain the fight against colonialism, on the eve of independence, number of them began to switch their loyalty to their individual ethnic groups with the belief that their political relevancy can only be sustained through the security of the ethnic base. This act formed the basis of ethnic politics in Nigeria.

The manifestation of ethnicism in Nigerian politics began when Zik left the Nigerian Youth Movement; it became almost Yoruba party proved when Chief Obafemi Awolowo also left with some members to transform a former Yoruba cultural organization (Egbe Omo Oduduwa) to Action Group party. In order to make clearer the aspiration of the party one of the Yoruba's leaders, Sir Adeyemo Alakija had stated, thus, 'the Yoruba will not be relegated on the background in future'. From the research, the main objective of the Action Group party 'was to create and actively foster the idea of a single nationalism throughout Yoruba land and to co-operate with existing ethnical and regional association'. The Northern People's Congress (NPC) had copied the Yoruba version of 'Egbe Omo Oduduwa', when the following Northern elites like Malam Abubakar, Malam Aminu Kano etc formed a cultural organization name, 'Jami'yar Mutanen Arewa'. This particular cultural organization will transform to a political party almost immediately it was formed. In that regard, in these cultural organization laid the political aspiration and foundation of party politics of Nigeria.

As a political front, the transformed cultural organizations in Nigeria particularly the NPC their aims and aspirations, 'was not to usurp the authority of their natural rulers, but to help them in the proper discharge of their duties'. Invariably NPC was formed to be the mouthpiece of the Sarduna and the Emirs in Nigeria, such could not sincerely support the course of nation. To perpetuate cultural superiority is therefore responsible to the formation of the Jami'yar Mutanen Arewa'. In addition It is not hidden that NPC was therefore formed to project the thought and the wishes of the natural rulers over other ethnic groups in Nigeria. Considering the roles played by the Sarduna of Sokoto in the 1950s and 60s it is not farfetched say culturally Nigeria was seen as a conquered territory. The Sarduna, Alhaji Ahmadu Bello, who happened to be among the founding members of the cultural

organization Jami'yar Mutanen Arewa' saw his involvement as a medium to lay claim over Nigeria. It thus became obvious to say, that the Sarduana who was the grandson of Usman dan Fodio the founder of the Sokoto Empire became involved in Nigerian politics in order to maintain grips over the affairs of the North in particular and Nigeria as a whole.

It is therefore appropriate to adduce, that the NPC did not only serve as a political front for the North but also the rallying point for the dissemination of the Islamic culture to Nigeria. This has continued to reflect in deviance to a secular Nigerian political terrain with some Governors from the North having at one time or the other declaring to implement of the Islamic Shania.

As the colonialism was coming to an end, Sarduana and some prominent Emirs with the Northern elites have formed strong and formidable clique with the British support on how to run or influence permanently the post colonial leadership in Nigeria. This is in aberration to the course of nation building. It should be recalled that ethnic politics have been practiced more in the North than the rest of the Country. For instance, 'in the dry season of 1951-52, Nigeria's first general election ... NPC, which was transformed half way through the election from a cultural organization into a political party, determined to secure the North for Northerners... swept the North'. Sincerely this worked against freedom of choice since some of the elections conducted in the North, voters were intimidated to votes only for the NPC.

Ethnic politics and anti-social behavior also played out when in 1964, Dr. Michael Okpara the then Premier Akintola of the Eastern Region decided to visit the western region, 'On the first day of his arrival in western Nigeria, Dr. Okpara went to pay Chief Akintola courtesy to at his official resident. But Chief Akintola was not at hand to receive his fellow Premier'. The cold reception given to Dr. Okpara aptly defined the extent to which ethnic politics in Nigeria was. The situation has not changed over sixty years after independence.

ETHNICISM AND NATION BUILDING IN NIGERIA.

Nigeria as a nation has continued to wander in the politics of ethnic wilderness due the absence of the integrative paraphernalia needed to foster national integration. The absence of truly and genuinely nationalistic figure has continued to undermine the course of nation building. Nwabughuogu aptly captured the key challenges to nation building in Africa when he stated, thus, 'the foremost problem militating against the nation building in Africa is the absence of nationalism in any country in the continent before independence and the failure to develop it during colonial rule'. Again if we consider the strength of nationalism which is strong devotion to one's country, we can only but agree with Nwabughuogu over the weakness in the development of national consciousness.

Nigeria over the years has failed to produce sustainable national ideology, propelled by nationalist figure, but rather ethnic jingoist, presumed to be nationalists, but whose desire or aspiration had been to sit on national platform to promote selfish interest. Secondly, there are those who supported Nigerian unity, simply because they wanted to retain ethnic popularity coming from the national popularity. Thirdly, there are still those who believed that since the unholy accord has been consummated the only option left is to aspire to climb up for the sake of pertaining in the sharing of the national cake. Obviously such mentalities would not promote Nationalism, and this is what nation is living with.

Mistrust has undermined the scenario necessary for the creation of nationally acceptable leaders. In that respect, a nationalist is like an institution that is laden with enduring ideology acceptable for all for the sake of projecting enduring legacies. With regard to the above

assertion, people must first of all and whole heartedly aspire to identify a nation before creating nationalists who will subsequently lead such nation. In order to actualize such nation Nwabughuogu stated, thus, 'In Africa, this type of nation did not exist, rather there existed many ethnic societies most times in conflict with one another and each with its loyalty to the small ethnic groups'. Again Onwudiwe affirmed the negative approach of the leaders to national issues as the reason for the growing ethnic loyalty when he stated, thus, 'these divergent opinions and differences stemmed from the distrust these leaders had of each other; they were each other's worst enemy'. Ethnic nationalism that would later engulf Nigeria was made strong through selfish politicking of the elites, whose selfish political ambition overshadowed sacrifices for national interest

During the colonial era, the northern Nigeria in order to catch up with the more politically advanced Eastern and Western Nigeria of Nigeria, resorted to hold tenaciously to Islamic traditions in the face of strong challenges from the western culture or ideology. Michael Crowder, again pointed out, 'Until Richards constitution the North was largely isolated from the south and since its traditional form of government had largely been preserved, there was little opportunity for western-style politics'.

As mentioned earlier, fear of domination informed by the strong northern attachment in support of ethnic politics, in fact, Crowder again pointed this out, thus, 'this was particularly true of the NPC, where long administrative separation from the south and relative political backwardness made their leaders genuinely afraid of southern domination, a point which the leader of NPC, the Sarduna of Sokoto, makes very clear in his autobiography'.

Ethnicism has continued to grow in leaps and bounds because it received strong foundation during the colonial rule, in divide and rule. Orjiakor and Unachukwu pointed that out in their work, with regard to the attitudes of the newly elected leaders during the colonial and early post colonial era. In respect to that they opined, thus, 'the preoccupation of these political elites was the distribution of the national cake including political offices, positions in the federal civil service, allocation and sitting of federal establishment and industries. All these were politicized along ethnic lines in total disregard for economic and social merit'. Again, because the elected leaders were hoisted through fraudulent and charades of election, selfish interest has continued to undermine national consciousness. Ethnic politics has received fillip because the key players in the political arena lack ideological discipline.

From the 1950s, during the time of Mr. E.E. Esua the then National Electoral Commissioner, through the times of Profs. Attahiru Jega and Mahmud Yakubu Nigeria has experienced the worst electoral process. In fact, Sally Dyson has this to say with regard to 1965 Federal Election in Nigeria, 'During the 1965 general election many candidates were returned unopposed because nominations from opponents were refused'. Ethnicity has continued to widen because of the politics of 'do or die', and this is against the concept of nation-building. As a result, the under aged children have been often used by politicians. With such political behavior it is obvious that Nigerian politician still lack the precept to prompt national interest. This attitude has become gangrenous spreading to other facet of social life. Nepotism has replaced national consciousness because fear of domination has gained the physic of the people of Nigeria.

While it is true that certain factors have contributed to falter the concept of nation building, attention have not been adequately focused on those challenges. Before the coming of the Europeans the Jihad of Usman dan Fodio has tended to capture the entirety of modern Nigeria with the motives of promoting Islamization. The British Colonial knows the History

better .When they amalgamated the southern and northern protectorates in 1914 what was the motives? As noted by Chinweizu, it was to unify administrations and not peoples'. From the above account, the British never encouraged the development or encouraged the development of Nationalism. By handing over the administration of Nigeria to Islamic leaders of the north, they indirectly encouraged the continuation of the Jihad, so strong ethnic politics exhibited by the northern politicians was countered by other ethnic groups in southern Nigeria.

Another devastating blow to the development of Nationalism 'was the inability of these leaders, who emerged immediately after independence to restructure and transform these colonial institutions left behind by British colonial government'. All these challenges have conspired to undermine the process of nation building in Nigeria.

British influence over her Nigerian colonial territory, projected both positive and negative impact. On the negative aspect, the unequal political development between the southern and the northern protectorates created sense mutual suspicions, this translated to the fear of political domination by the north. Educationally the North were not ready to compete with the more educated south because they have less manpower to superintend the administration of the independence north. This is rooted in the people's ideology, and tended to have sustained ethnicity, thereby undermining the concept of nation building in Nigeria.

With regard to the consequences of ethnicity on nation building, the truth remains that, 'most African countries are bereft of functional ideologies and this has affected their process of nation building'. Again colonial ideology has taken firm grips of African mentality, this led to an ideology anchored within the dictate of time demand. For instance, during the colonial era, the key ideologies of the elites were the building of University for Africa, the application of equal pay in the colonial civil service and the creation of job opportunities for the whites and engagement of more Africans in elective positions. These and many more were the preoccupation of the Africans. In effect, at that level Africans were only yawning for accommodation in the colonial government. These demands however fall short of ideals for nation building.

In addition, the literacy level of Africa was low. So many of them could not understand the essence of developing indigenous ideology .The inferiority complex also undermined the development of any form of ideology that would propel national consciousness for the sake of nation building.

CONCLUSION.

The ethnic groups that constitute Nigeria now were living apart but united economically and related socially unhindered before the coming of the Europeans. Why have they now come to realize, their differences now that they have come under one political umbrella as the British creation? I think the reason is not farfetched. Firstly, factors supporting ethnicity did not just happen, it took thousands of years, beside it happened to group who have lived together over those years. Again over those years groups have been able to develop the strength of the union and have held tenaciously to it. For instance, political life of every group symbolizes the strength of the group. It is where loyalty and power of the group resides. Politics control the economic and social behavior of every group. Whereas a group could accommodate and promote economic or inter-group relationship and moderate social behavior with regards to supporting cultural diffusion, it cannot hand off voluntarily its political leaders which is her symbol of strength. In that respect, the strength of political authority has remained very strong because no group would gladly handover her political authority by appeal without reservation and a fight if need be.

In that regard, the traditional political institution is not only strong but formidable, because they lie not only the identity of a group but the history of the group. The British colonial administrators noticed that among the Hausa/Fulani cohesive political institution took exceptional love of their system. Whereas they allowed the indigenous political institution of North to remain intact, they decided to alter the political institution of groups they referred to as stateless societies. That act alone marked the beginning of ethnic consciousness.

Again, if ethnicity means human groups who have a conviction that 'they have a common identity and common goal because they have common origin'. Considering the above definition of ethnicity, then the conviction to collectively become a nation is needed to be galvanized towards promoting sense of nationalism. The question, was such tendency available to the groups in Niger-area when they were amalgamated by the British in 1914? The answer is no. The how do we expect political rancor due to such failure not to generate political hullabaloo when the British created nation of Nigeria in 1960.

The newly independent Nigeria experienced ethnic politics anchored on the survival of the fittest, because the groups were lump together by the British in an awkward manner that failed to address the issue of fear of domination. This fear was created by the British government who deliberately and glaringly expressed their love to the Hausa/Fulani to the point of granting to them the privilege of controlling the political authority of the country prior to independence.

The newly empowered political leaders in Nigeria on their own failed to correct the mistakes of the colonial administrators, when they began to ply the scripts of ethnic agenda. In fact, Orjiakor and Unachukwu, have contended the danger of this British creation, when they stated, thus, 'But at independence there were several potential dangers to Nigeria's continued existence. The then Northern Region encompassed more than two thirds of the area of the Country and there were fears in the south that the Northern based NPC might perpetuate itself in power at the federal level'.

Since independence, various leaders of Nigeria of Nigeria has never exhibited any sincere approach to peaceful co-existence, policy thrust of leaders have always betrayed attempts of hoisting ethnic politics thereby widening the gulf of nepotism.

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